

Evaluation of Educational Content Sharing Solutions: Challenges of the mEducator Best Practice Network

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Abstract: The Best Practice Network (BPN) for medical education (mEducator) aims at implementing and critically evaluating existing standards and reference models in order to address a lack of standardized mechanisms for medical educational content sharing. As part of this work two solutions will be implemented to provide platforms for discovering, sharing, retrieving, repurposing and re-using medical educational content. There is currently no standardized way of evaluating these solutions; however there are other systems and Web2.0 platforms that have commonalities with the mEducator solutions and as such can share aspects of their evaluation approaches. This study reviews the literature to critically compare these approaches, identify points of convergence of their evaluation requirements with mEducator and propose a blueprint for the development of an evaluation framework for assessing the effectiveness of the platforms that will be implemented through the mEducator BPN and any future platforms that attempt to address the same issues.

Introduction - Outlining the problem

Although there is an abundance of medical educational content available in individual EU academic institutions, this is not widely available or easy to discover and retrieve, due to lack of standardized content sharing mechanisms. The purpose of the mEducator best practice network (BPN) (www.meducator.net) is to critically evaluate existing standards and models in the field of e-learning in order to enable state-of-the art medical educational content to be discovered, retrieved, shared, repurposed and re-used across European higher academic institutions. For this purpose, mEducator investigates if existing standards for educational material packaging and exchange among learning management systems are adequate to support state-of-the art educational content sharing in medicine and provides recommendations for standards extensions. The mEducator BPN is implementing two state of the art solutions for content sharing, namely, a solution based on Web2.0 technologies, and a solution based on Semantic Web Services. These solutions enable locating and accessing data and also repurposing and sharing data from many different sources. mEducator addresses several learning contexts ranging from traditional instructional teaching to active learning and experiential teaching/studying approaches. It furthermore includes many different content types, ranging from text to exam sheets, algorithms, teaching files, computer programs (simulators, serious games) and interactive objects (like virtual patients and digital tracings of anatomies), while it covers a variety of tools.

These two solutions need to be evaluated so that we can assess the impact of their key differences to the quality of service they provide and their overall viability. The present paper briefly describes the two mEducator solutions and explains why the evaluation of mEducator, which is different compared to any Learning Content Management System (LCMS), information retrieval or Web2.0 platform requires a specifically crafted, comprehensive evaluation approach. A review of the literature on evaluation models applied to systems that, at least in some aspect, have points of convergence with mEducator, such as e-learning platforms, content sharing solutions, digital libraries (DL), and systems specifically designed for the medical domain revealed several dimensions and key issues that are critical to consider from a methodological and conceptual point of view. The contribution of this work lies in the identification of issues pertaining to the evaluation of state-of-the-art educational content sharing solutions. As a result, a blueprint is provided for the development of an evaluation framework for platforms that enable the retrieval of educational content, using the medical domain as an example.

mEducator: a BPN for retrieving medical educational content

To support their teaching, institutions often use a variety of web-based LCMS and educational

standards which are developed and adopted to enable the universal description of educational content, namely, IEEE Learning Object Metadata (LOM), and SCORM (Buendia & Hervas, 2006). To implement efficient brokerage mechanisms for educational content sharing, mashup technologies have recently been used. Web 2.0 applications through the use of mashup technologies offer new opportunities for health education since they allow open access to information, sharing of ideas, questions, and opinions. But, current e-learning research indicates that access to comprehensive repositories of learning objects and metadata is the crucial factor in the future of e-learning and the vision of interoperability. There is a need therefore for an efficient brokerage mechanism for educational content sharing. Two are being developed and evaluated by the mEducator BPN.

The first proposed solution develops a brokerage mechanism based on RSS feeds, “mashup” technology and other Web 2.0 technologies. It is based on work performed by the MEDTING project (<http://medting.com>), an internet website for the exchange of clinical cases, medical images and videos, which also features the MEDTING Connectors technology that allows content to be shared among other websites. This solution assumes independent content repositories on the web and uses mashup technologies for accessing content from external websites, thus creating a loosely coupled LCMS network. RSS technology is employed to add user generated content as per the Health2.info best practice initiative (<http://health20.org>).

The second solution proposed in mEducator is designed around a federated architecture based on a service-oriented application framework and the use of semantic technologies. The utilized framework is fundamentally based on the Semantic Web Services-oriented e-learning architecture (Dietze, Gugliotta & Domingue, 2008) developed as part of the LUISA project (<http://www.luisa-project.eu>) which was updated and improved to reflect on mEducator-specific requirements as well as the emerging Linked Data and Linked Services (Pedrinaci & Domingue, 2010) paradigms. As such, this solution fundamentally exploits semantic representations of data and services to provide interoperability between e-learning repositories spread across the Web.

Current evaluation models

Evaluation is a fundamental aspect in any project involving the design, implementation and deployment of an innovation. It is a complex and multifaceted task that might be carried out with a range of methods, often domain specific. The key dimensions to take into account when designing an evaluation plan are the: “What” is going to be evaluated (e.g., a program, an instructional unit, a tool, and in what domain); and the “Purpose” of the evaluation (i.e., how the result of the evaluation will be used, e.g., to improve the design, to better understand a process and so forth). In general, an evaluation model is a framework that can be used to assist in the definition of the parameters of an evaluation, what concepts to focus on, and the processes and methods needed to gather the critical data, thus it shapes the research questions and informs the overall process of inquiry.

The challenges involved in crafting an evaluation plan are related to the degree of novelty of the system. When there is experience, a typical approach to evaluation is based on benchmarking, which involves comparing aspects of performance of the system with those of existing, reference solutions. The assumption is that the dimensions of quality, or the features that concur to quality, have been empirically determined. However, for an innovative system such as the mEducator proposed solutions, the first step of the evaluation is actually the identification of such dimensions and of their relative importance.

To derive broad specifications to consider when designing a comprehensive evaluation framework for mEducator, the following literatures have been reviewed: evaluation models for e-learning platforms, content sharing solutions, and DL, since each of these systems has some commonality with mEducator.

Evaluation models for e-learning platforms

A review of the literature concerning evaluation models for e-learning platforms showed that several characteristics should be taken into account starting from the function and usability of the learning system in the context of the human, social and cultural organization within which it is to be used (Colace, De Santo & Pietrosanto, 2006). Previous researchers attempted to define a methodology for systematically evaluating e-learning applications and platforms focusing on usability and accessibility, focusing on adaptation issues and courseware re-use (Graf & List, 2005), using analytic hierarchy processes (Colace et al., 2006) or using standard specifications and benchmark tests (Buendia & Hervas, 2006).

One aspect in which these researchers agree is that it is important to understand how the features of the system are integrated to facilitate learning or training and what principles are applied to guide the way the system is used. Therefore, for evaluation purposes, pedagogical, technological and usability aspects must be taken into account (Colace et al., 2006). Moreover, for suggesting a framework for the evaluation of e-learning platforms, it seems that multiple criteria decision-making approaches should be implemented, as those approaches are useful in circumstances which necessitate the consideration of different courses of action, which

cannot be evaluated by the measurement of a simple, single dimension. Colace et al. (2006) for instance, introduced a general and objective model using relative weights for important criteria for describing, characterizing and selecting e-learning platforms, which took into account both the platform and its services and the scenario of its use in different organizations. Along the same lines, Buendia & Hervas (2006) described an evaluation framework called the “Learning Platform Evaluation Model”, based on the use of standard specifications (SCORM), which organizes the functionalities of any learning platform into three areas: content, communications and management. Their model is based on the idea of benchmark tests based on the functions and tools that are needed in a platform.

A common aspect of evaluation models used for e-learning platforms that mEducator can benefit from refers to the importance of content quality. However, one of the limitations of the model proposed by Colace et al. (2006) is the fact that it evaluates an e-learning platform considering its application in three hypothesized scenarios in comparison with four considered platforms. Along the same lines, Buendia & Hervas’ work (2006) was also based on the comparison of two existing platforms. In the case of mEducator, the primary purpose is neither the comparison with other information retrieval platforms, as its purpose is unique, nor to focus only on the comparison of the two suggested solutions within mEducator, as those share the same metadata scheme. In addition to this, the scenarios of its use are numerous as it addresses the needs of many different types of users, such as students, educators, doctors and health professionals. The blueprint of the development of an evaluation framework for mEducator therefore has to account for those different needs by taking the dimension of the users into consideration.

Evaluation models for content sharing solutions

Evaluation models or case studies explicitly addressing the technical infrastructure for content sharing and contributing contents mostly refer to peer to peer (P2P) and semantic web services technology. Zhou et al. (2010) evaluated “Lesson”, a system for searching and sharing lecture notes featuring a peer-to-peer overlay network to share the content and a metasearch engine to access them. The system merges results from multiple component search engines and this is achieved according to a strategy that takes into account rank, similarity and features of the lecture notes. In a P2P system a typical focus of evaluation is performance of the query routing mechanism adopted by the network to locate the content in the available peers, that is measured in terms of response time plus query hit rate and bandwidth consumption. Evaluations of the mechanism for merging results are carried out through comparison with general purpose search engines, and some existing metasearch schemes.

Srinivasan et al. (2006) focused on the performance evaluation of OWL-S-based semantic web services. They benchmarked the performance of their system with that of a UDDI registry on two dimensions: publishing time (time to publish and advertise on a registry) and querying time (time to process a query). Wu and Xia (2008) proposed a model for evaluating Quality of Service (QOS) for semantic web services; they pointed out the need to use both general and domain specific indicators, to be defined by an expert. These are important in order to choose the right web service. Examples are: Time – time to complete task requested by users (response time including execution time); Cost – resources used by Web services or cost paid by users; Reliability – ability to supply the service (failure rate, success rate); Security – trustworthiness (authentication, confidentiality etc); Reputation – evaluation by users (click rating, customer satisfaction).

Watson et al. (2010) identified some features and functionalities that make repositories attractive to their intended users. These features include: 1) ease of publication to the web –regardless of size or file type, 2) structures to support personal engagement with a community of users, such as an enhanced profile page, space for user comments, ratings and other quality indicators, 3) ways of personalizing user engagement, for example through personal lists of ‘most viewed’ or ‘most downloaded’ and bookmarking of favorites, and 4) a clearly open “look and feel”, which encourages sharing of information and files, and does not mandate metadata.

Evaluation models for digital libraries (DL)

The development of a theoretical framework for Evaluation of DL, together with appropriate methodologies, has been one the foci of the “Delos” project, a Network of Excellence on DL (<http://www.delos.info/>). The main lessons from this effort are summarized in Fuhr et al. (2008), who pointed out the inherent complexity of defining a comprehensive evaluation framework, given the multitude of perspectives that are involved, and also acknowledged that some aspects are still controversial. Two interesting evaluation models stand out from their review. The first one is the “Triptych model”, which is based on three areas of interest: System, Content, Users. These are connected through the following conceptual interrelations that, in turn identify additional axes for evaluation: System – Content are related through *Performance* (to point out that some aspects of a system’s performance depend on the formats, structures and representation of the contents); User – Systems are related through *Usability* (a usable system is easy to learn, flexible, etc.); Content – Users are related through *Usefulness* (to point out that content must be useful and relevant to the user’s task).

The second evaluation model involves: *Construct* (what to evaluate, in particular, what service); *Context* (scenarios, actors, objectives and goals, approaches and perspective in the study), *Criteria* (covers parameters, factors and measures used to assess the quality of what is evaluated and every aspect of a DL being evaluated) and *Methodology* (describes the procedures and protocols followed in both the gathering and the analysis of data from the evaluation experiment.) In their final recommendations, Fuhr et al. (2008) called for evaluation of “user behavior in-the-large” (as opposed to the focus on user interface and system issues) i.e., user satisfaction with respect to their information needs, and the determination of users’ search and tactics (e.g., search strategies and browsing behavior). This would complement the precision and recall measures used traditionally in the evaluation of Information Retrieval systems. Precision is defined as the fraction of retrieved documents that are relevant to the query, and recall as the fraction of the items that are relevant to the query and are successfully retrieved. This approach rests on the notion of relevance (defined by a panel of experts) and on the availability of a test bed collection. However, recently this has been challenged in the case where information retrieval tasks involved learning and/or judgment on the part of the user through an open-ended activity, often with prolonged effort over sessions and users’ adaptation of their goals and strategies (Kelly, 2009).

Moreira et al. (2007) proposed a quality model for DL, considering accessibility, accuracy, completeness, composability, conformance, consistency, effectiveness, efficiency, extensibility, pertinence, preservability, relevance, reliability, reusability, significance, similarity, and timeliness. Regarding measurement, they considered characteristics like: response time (with regard to efficiency), and number of service failures (to assess reliability). Saracevic (2005) identified the following dimensions that deserve consideration: 1) Information representation, metadata and surrogates used in the DL. Examples of information representation and surrogates are: extraction of key phrases, noun phrasing in medical DL, abstract viewable, text snippets and so on; 2) Tools (linking, sophisticated multimedia search features, etc.); and 3) Services (e.g., recommender systems and the like). Xie (2008) studied the evaluation of DLs from the user perspective, trying to understand what issues are most relevant to the users. The lessons to be drawn are that this can be community specific, and that the joint use of sophisticated log analysis and interviews is recommended.

In comparison with DLs, in mEducator there are no institutionalized stakeholders, such as librarians. Repurposing tasks are not supported in DLs and that is a need identified as unique to mEducator in this respect. Points of convergence are: 1) domain specialization, 2) a repository (or federated repositories) of metadata is queried, 3) no particular assumption is made on the nature of the content (although in the DL the prevalence is digital text) and 4) Services can be designed and offered to the users.

Evaluation of systems of the medical domain

A common evaluation aspect of systems designed specifically for the medical domain is the efficacy of the search and retrieval functions. The prime example is PubMed (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed>), a free database accessing the MEDLINE database of citations (<http://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/factsheets/medline.html>), abstracts and some full text articles on life sciences and biomedical topics. Since PubMed does not rely on user supplied content, but rather on an authoritative source it does not need to deal with any of the issues related to the mEducator proposed solutions with regard to user provided or generated content. Therefore, in this study, we focus on the search functionality for medical content, which is an evaluation concern shared with mEducator.

A study on how users find things with Pubmed (Lin & Smucker, 2008) outlined how in the context of document retrieval in the biomedical domain, there is a complex relationship between the quality of initial query results and the overall utility of an interactive retrieval system. They studied the efficacy of a content similarity browsing tool for compensating poor retrieval results, and the relationship of retrieval performance and overall utility. The authors utilized a user simulation technique to evaluate the performance of different search and browsing strategies. The applicability of user simulations was demonstrated as a formative tool for automatic utility evaluation. They proposed simulation-based studies as an additional evaluation tool to complement interactive and Crandfield style experiments. Due to the diverse nature of the roles, background knowledge and cultural background of the users of mEducator, who are expected to be people in the medical domain from all levels, fields and European countries, it is possible that any attempt to use user generated evaluation of retrieval results on the two proposed solutions will be biased on both the relationship of each content seeker to the content provider as well as the familiarity of each user to each of the proposed solution or LCMS system that the retrieved content resides on. The concept of simulation based studies is an interesting approach since it removes this bias, even though it does not replace user generated evaluation approaches.

Implications for mEducator

An a priori analysis of the goals and nature of the mEducator solutions points out five important pillars for supporting the process of mEducator that need to be addressed in an evaluation model: 1) Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of content (refers to license types and mechanisms of content protection), 2) Repurposing

(refers to documentation of content genealogy and content reuse activities), 3) Metadata scheme, 4) Content evaluation (system generated analyses, user review, peer review process) and 5) Content sharing.

At the same time, three dimensions are transversal and span across those pillars. These refer to: a) Human computer interaction (HCI) (accessibility, usability, consistency), b) Technological issues (requirements for content providers, handling of content updates, system performance and maintenance requirements) and c) Sustainability (Incentives for content providers/consumers/reviewers and financial sustainability).

Based on the lessons derived from the literature review of evaluation models in different domains, and the identified pillars of mEducator we next attempt to identify the connections between the two and propose the blueprint of an evaluation framework applicable to mEducator and to systems that face the same challenges. The literature review indicated that systems that have evaluation concerns similar to mEducator pertaining the first pillar, IPR of content, are digital libraries (Zhang, 2007), peer-to-peer and social networks. Systems concerned with the second pillar, repurposing, are mostly LCMSs where adaptation issues and courseware reuse (Rego et al. 2009; Graf & List, 2005) are addressed. Metadata, the third pillar, are implemented in a variety of systems, such as DL and information retrieval systems, e-learning systems, search engines and public libraries such as PubMed, where there are several open issues, such as the identification of the best metadata approach depending on the requirements of the system, the role of metadata to support retrieval and adaptability to the user, and the evaluation of search and retrieval functionalities of public libraries (Hoogendam, et al. 2009). The fourth and fifth pillar, content evaluation and content sharing are central concerns in peer review systems, P2P systems, DL and search engines, among others, and unresolved issues refer to the evaluation of social tagging of metadata (Zens & Baumgartner, 2008) and the collaborative evaluation of content by users and experts (Rego et al, 2009).

Blueprint for the development of an evaluation framework for mEducator

Based on the insight from the literature analysis, we present a blueprint for the evaluation of the mEducator project, by identifying, for each key dimension of evaluation, examples of relevant criteria/metrics, typologies of questions that should be asked, and, when relevant, pointing out the issues and criticalities that are specific to mEducator.

<p>SYSTEM</p> <p>Technological infrastructure <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> Performance, Cost, Deployment effort, Maintenance, Reliability, Scalability, Interoperability <i>Type of questions:</i> Is there any impact of underlying technology on the type of services and tools that can be built on top? What are the relative advantages of the two mEducator solutions? <i>Issues:</i> Is there a need to benchmarking with P2P solutions? Since each technology has technical performance indicators of radically different nature (e.g., time to register and publish a service), if these aspects are analyzed, they should be related to global performance indicators meaningful to the end-user (e.g., overall response time).</p> <p>Tools and functions <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> Task appropriateness, Performance, Cost-effectiveness, Usability, Usefulness <i>Type of questions:</i> Are there tools and functions available to support the user tasks? Is their design and implementation adequate and usable? Do they support the key processes of the system: i.e. search, navigate, browse, evaluate a resource, obtain a resource, share a resource, repurpose a resource? <i>Issues:</i> Usability criteria apply both at the level of single functions and tools at the system general level.</p> <p>Services <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> Performance, Composability, Extensibility, Reusability, User satisfaction, Usefulness <i>Type of questions:</i> Do the services available provide added value to the user? Is there any impact of underlying technology on the type of services and tools that can be built on top? What are the relative advantages of the two mEducator solutions? <i>Issues:</i> Personalization and recommendation services</p> <p>General <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> Learnability, Ease of use, Time to complete tasks, Confidence in the results, Satisfaction, Success, Impact, Quality of the experience, Barriers <i>Questions:</i> What factors affect user acceptance of the system?</p>	<p>CONTENT</p> <p>Shared content <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> Accessibility, Availability, Quality, Timeliness, Coverage, Overlap <i>Type of questions:</i> Is the quality of the shared content adequate for the user tasks? How does user-generated content affect retrieval performance and user perceptions of usefulness of the system? <i>Issues:</i> need to evaluate quality of single resources and collection of resources (same site provenance, for example), counterbalancing “cold starts” of the system</p> <p>Content representation, system performance <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> metadata completeness and accuracy, search and retrieval effectiveness and efficiency <i>Type of questions:</i> How does the selected metadata schema impact search and retrieval performance?</p> <p>Content representation, user performance <i>Examples of evaluation criteria:</i> metadata completeness and accuracy, search and retrieval effectiveness and efficiency, metadata provenance, conformance to expectation, logical consistency and coherence, timeliness, accessibility, utility of metadata and of folksonomies for finding relevant content, <i>Type of questions:</i> How does search results presentation (surrogates, ranking, etc.) affect user perceptions of usefulness of the system? Can users use social tagging of metadata? If automatic metadata generation is used how does it compare to expert indexing?</p>
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Figure 1: Blueprint for the development of an evaluation framework for mEducator

The System component has been split in Technological infrastructure, Tools, Services and General aspects, whereas the Content component includes aspects of interrelations between content representation and system and user performance, respectively (see Figure1). In general, interrelations between system, user, and contents are taken into account wherever usability and usefulness are mentioned.

Conclusion

The goal of this study was to perform a literature review of the existing evaluation techniques available that could be applied on a platform that would enable medical educational content to be discovered, retrieved, shared, repurposed and re-used. The evaluation approaches of different systems, such as e-learning platforms, content sharing solutions, digital libraries, interactive information retrieval systems and systems specifically applicable to the medical domain were reviewed. Points of convergence of their evaluation requirements with the mEducator solutions have been identified. As a result, a blueprint was created for the development of an evaluation framework for assessing the effectiveness of platforms that will be implemented through the mEducator BPN and any future platforms that attempt to address the same issues.

By utilizing the evaluation blueprint that resulted from the work done in this study, the evaluation framework that will be developed by the mEducator BPN can inherit several aspects from existing well established evaluation platforms, thus creating a more robust evaluation approach. Key aspects of the mEducator evaluation were identified that were not covered by other systems, and the mEducator BPN will need to focus on those in order to define new evaluation approaches that address them.

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